

APPLICATION OF NETWORK DESIGN TOOL TO TACTICAL MOBILE AD HOC NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

NEDAT (Network Engineering Design and Analysis Toolset) is an engineering tool being developed by US Army RDECOM-CERDEC to assist network designers in the design and construction of mobile ad hoc networks based on end-user performance goals and requirements. This paper will introduce and describe the functionality of the current version of NEDAT (v2.1) and to show how it can be used in designing MANETs (Mobile Ad Hoc Networks). Results produced by the tool will help network designers to choose optimum components and parameters (e.g. protocols, transmit power) for the network to meet or exceed the stated performance goals. A description of the areas focused in the networking design space will be presented.

1. INTRODUCTION

Military communications is relying more on wireless mobile ad hoc network (MANETs) as they continue to adopt the network-centric paradigm. It is challenging to create reliable wireless networks that must carry demanding traffic loads of various requirements (delay, rate, loss, duration) over dynamic and harsh RF conditions (mobility, terrain, jamming). One of the major difficulties in designing MANETs is that the multi-hop connectivity, as provided by RF propagation, is a stochastic process as is the applied traffic load. This is rather different from the traditional wired networks, where the connectivity is static or nearly so. In the familiar digital cellular networks, only the link between the subscriber and base station is RF, and typically no direct subscriber-to-subscriber communication is permitted. In addition, the double stochastic nature of MANETS (i.e. the connectivity and applied traffic load) leads to great difficulties in getting tractable mathematical performance models. Hence, MANET design has been more of an art than a science. In addition, the behavior of such MANETs is not well understood, and frequent surprises occur when actual networks are built and tested in both lab and field environments.

The situation is changing however, through the application of results obtained through the emerging field of Network Science. Network Science has as one of its primary goals the modeling and understanding of all types of networks, including traditional packet based MANETs. By using sophisticated mathematical modeling, and observing behaviors in all classes of networks (biological, chemical, social, etc), it is believed that a greater understanding of and performance characterization of MANET will result. NEDAT will directly use these emerging results from Network Science and integrate them into a sophisticated tool that can be used to accurately design MANETs that when built and tested, provide the required performance and functionality. This should ultimately lead to better network designs for the Army at reduced development cost.

CERDEC is developing Network Engineering Design Analytical Toolset (NEDAT) to assist network designers and engineers choose optimum components and parameters (e.g. protocols and transmit powers) for their future wireless ad hoc network. Currently, no such tools exist that design (or help design) wireless ad hoc networks. The traditional method of designing ad hoc networks typically relies on using a discrete event simulation language, such as OPNET or QUALNET, to model the designed network and to compute its resultant performance under a fixed set of input conditions and parameters. Network performance curves are possible only through repeated simulation executions with differing parameter values. In addition, currently available techniques do not include the concept of optimality in the design, so the human designer is not aware of the fundamental performance capable of the design. NEDAT uniquely mitigates these limitations by using sophisticated analytic performance models for critical network functions, such as topology control, routing, and TDMA slot assignment, and then uses conventional optimization techniques such as simulated annealing (SA) and linear programming (LP), to produce the “best” design possible. This paper covers the current version (v2.1) of the NEDAT tool as of the writing of this paper May 2008. An earlier version of NEDAT is described in [1,2,3].

2. NEDAT OVERVIEW

NEDAT allows for a relatively quick comparison of network performance and performance bounds resulting from a chosen set of network communication components (e.g. type of routing, clustering, MAC algorithm etc.) and parameters (e.g. transmit power maximum, SINR, slot size, etc.). This is done by applying optimization techniques (e.g. Simulated Annealing and linear programming) and heuristics to optimize network given performance goals and network constraints. Figure 1 shows a high-level conceptual diagram of NEDAT functionality.

Figure 1: (U) Conceptual diagram of NEDAT.

The underlying network design algorithms are collected from research in the growing field of Network Science and are described in detail in [3]. These algorithms assess network at different layers over a variety of parameters. They do not focus on specific protocols but instead use representative or classes of protocols in order to avoid the details of similar protocols with only minor variations.

The most important network parameters that NEDAT tries to optimize are connectivity, capacity, delay, and survivability. Connectivity is the ability for any node to connect to another node in the network with some probability. To achieve this requirement, NEDAT tries to avoid network partitioning of the node locations, which is typically provided as a set of node coordinates and RF path loss between nodes. Capacity is the maximum rate of information that can be exchanged between all pairs of end-to-end users. Alternatively, NEDAT tries to design a network that fulfills an input traffic load set, such as delay and survivability constraints. Survivability implies that network should

not become partitioned in spite of the loss of some nodes or links. An integer K , requiring K disjoint paths between node pairs, is used to address the survivability requirement; and is specified as an input by the network designer.

Since the design space for wireless communication is overwhelmingly vast, our network design algorithms and optimization methods are focused only on a few key areas. At this current phase of development, the network design functions being optimized are topology control, routing algorithm selections, and MAC algorithm selection as described below. Fairly simple models are used for the radio hardware (currently limited to maximum transmitter power, receiver sensitivity, and maximum signaling rate). Overhead is represented by a fractional loss in link capacity for security overhead, routing overhead and MAC (header) overhead. Multicast and link layer QoS are also being considered for future enhancements in FY08/09.

2.1 HIGH LEVEL DESCRIPTION OF NEDAT OPERATION

NEDAT designs the network through a strict sequence of functions calls to specific algorithms that compute that function. The functions are grouped into modules, where a module may include a different software function (written in C) to design a network functionality. The current NEDAT is capable of running in two distinct modes: the Step-by-step mode and the Continuous mode. The Step-by-step mode operates on a specific time instance of the scenario, while the continuous mode operates over the entire scenario duration. Consequently, the effects of mobility in the ad hoc network are represented through a set of static snapshots of a mobile scenario.

The Step-by-step mode will be described first. Each snapshot corresponds to a particular instant in time of the scenario, and includes specific values for node locations, path loss between nodes, and applied traffic load. After the initial input stage where the snapshot is indicated, topology control algorithm is executed to create the network connectivity (with survivability constraints if called for by the designer), then the routing algorithm selection algorithm is executed to provide the end to end paths to support the required input traffic flows, and finally the MAC algorithm is executed, that performs the detailed slot assignments for each link. It should be noted that at this point in the program, these functions are performed and optimized independently of each other. Future NEDAT capabilities will incorporate

a cross layer optimization technique that should lead to “more optimized” network designs.

Hence in the Step-by-step mode, the user steps through and views the results of the design sequence one stage at a time. The user is allowed to repeat current or previous stages with different algorithms and parameter settings to see the effects of those changes and to become more familiar with the network design algorithms functionality. In this mode, the design algorithms only operate on a single input snapshot of static nodes but the output of each stage is very detailed.

In Continuous mode, NEDAT automatically steps through the design sequence on multiple snapshots. The user selects all the design algorithms and parameters for every stage before running the experiment. To reduce the amount of data given back to the user, only the statistical minimum, maximum, and mean values of various algorithms over the snapshots are provided and displayed. Any anomalous results can be later investigated in Step-by-step mode for more details.

Currently, transient effects of mobility in the ad hoc network are not explicitly taken into account due to lack of (quantifiable) research available in this area. As a substitute, we are using a set of static snapshots of a mobile scenario. A network design that satisfies user performance requirements for all snapshots is then the one that should be selected.

Figure 2: (U) Snapshot of NEDAT’s GUI showing the tree, graphical, and tabular output views.

2.2 GRAPHICAL USER INTERFACE

In this section, the different components of the GUI (Figure 2) will be introduced. Figure 2 does not show the input dialog and the Continuous mode output charts. The GUI is where the user interacts with the design

algorithms by selecting algorithm parameters and executing algorithms through the input dialog. The resulting data is examined through the rest of the GUI panels, which will be described in the following sections.

2.2.1 TREE VIEW

On the side panel, output data from the stages (except for MAC) of Step-by-step mode is compactly organized in a tree. The potentially large amount of data is collapsed in the tree until the user expands the section he or she wishes to review. The tree view is very useful in that a large amount of data can be compactly displayed, and more details about that data can be expanded as needed or as of interest. For example, the routes are initially displayed only as a source-destination pair, but can be expanded to include all intermediate relay nodes and links if desired.

2.2.2 GRAPHICAL VIEW

The main panel on the GUI is used to visually display the results of the stages of Step-by-step mode (except for the MAC stage). Here the details about the node locations, links between nodes, traffic flows, and routes are shown and specific entities can be highlighted. All of the entities displayed are also linked with the data held in the tree view.

2.2.3 MAC TABLES

A set of tables is generated when the user executes the MAC module in Step-by-step mode. Output for this module contains detailed data, such as link/slot sets, traffic loss & delays, and channel utilization, which are better displayed in an organized tabular manner rather than a graphical one.

2.2.4 CONTINUOUS MODE CHARTS

Output for Continuous mode is a set of summary data from each module per snapshot. This is done because detailed output from every module on every snapshot can potentially generate enormous amounts of data that could overwhelm the user. Most of the summary data are the statistical minimum, maximum, and mean values of the metrics calculated in Step-by-step mode.

The summary data is displayed in a set of line charts organized by the design sequence stage. This is the best way to view the results of individual metrics through the entire series of snapshot. Values that differ greatly against the rest of the snapshots will be shown as spikes

in the line graph which can be treated as an indicator to investigate how the network design configuration and snapshot created such anomalies.

When an error occurs during an algorithm's execution, data is not acquired from that erroneous snapshot and the next snapshot is then examined. In the chart, snapshots with errors are shown as gaps in the line graph and the specific snapshot errors are listed in a table in a separate tab. Currently, it is the user's task to investigate the error and to find its solution.

3. NETWORK DESIGN MODULES

Currently the NEDAT design includes five modules: node input, traffic input, topology control, routing, and MAC. As mentioned above, each module contained one or more C functions that can be used to implement a network function. The following sections will describe the purpose of each stage of the design sequence. Details on the current network design algorithms are in [4].

3.1 NODE LOCATIONS & TRAFFIC LOAD

Node location and traffic input is stored in files generated by the user. Node location files (snapshots) contain grid coordinates of each node and RF path loss between each node pair. Traffic files describe specific flows the network is required to deliver; these flows comprise of source and destination, data rate, duration, traffic type, and priority level. Other parameters to be set are the maximum transmit power limit of the nodes and the SINR required to establish communication between nodes.

In Step-by-step mode, details of the nodes and flows are displayed on the tree and are mapped graphically. This allows the user to view how the nodes are spread out and a give a place to review the traffic flow requirements.

3.2 TOPOLOGY CONTROL

The purpose of this stage is to find optimal transmit power level(s) for the nodes in order to minimize network power while achieving a network that is at least k -connected. NEDAT uses k -connectivity as its metric for survivability where k is a constraint given by the user. Currently, k -connectivity is implemented as node degree but in the next version of NEDAT it will be k number of independent paths from every source-destination pair.

There are two algorithms to select for topology control: a heuristic and a Simulated Annealing based algorithm. Depending on the size of the network, the heuristic algorithm has the benefit of producing a solution in a relatively short amount of time. Simulated Annealing is an approach for finding the stochastic approximation of the global optimum, in this case, to optimize minimum total transmits power.

For both algorithms, the user can choose to have homogeneous or heterogeneous transmit powers levels, in other words, to have all the nodes transmit at the same power or individual power settings. Selecting heterogeneity would be equivalent to giving the network adaptive power control, where each node could select its own optimal transmit power to achieve the desired network topology.

The output of these algorithms is the transmit power per node and the resulting links created between nodes. Statistics on node transmit powers can be used to estimate the energy required by the system. The diameter of the resulting connected network gives an estimate of the number of hops a flow will travel which is a factor into the delay of a flow. If output is produced, then the algorithm found a solution and the network is connected with no partitions (islands) and is at least k -connected. Otherwise, an error is given because the network is partitioned or failed to achieve k -connectedness as a result of one or more of these contributing factors: max transmit power limitation, receiver sensitivity (a user input), and/or node distribution. Current plans include the future addition of new design algorithms for this module that would determine the need for the addition and placement of a other nodes, such as UAV relays, to be added to the network to achieve the desired connectivity.

3.3 ROUTING

Routes are found to satisfy every traffic flow using a selected routing protocol scheme. One of the two available schemes to choose from is Dijkstra with the choice of cost function of either finding minimum hop count or minimum energy routes. The other is a quality of service (QoS) scheme that finds paths based on multiple criteria the user can select from.

At this stage, the user specifies percentages to reduce the link bandwidth (which is also a user input at this point in development) to accommodate the overhead of routing, MAC, and security protocols. This is a place holder for potential algorithms that would more accurately

calculate or estimate the overheads of the components of the network system.

The outcome of this stage shows where potential congested areas, hot spots, and bottle necks are in the snapshot under the selected routing scheme. The statistics on the amount of hops needed by the flows gives an estimate on the end-to-end delay. Also, statistics on the power used along the traffic flow routes gives insight into the energy needed by the network.

3.4 MAC

There are two TDMA-based MAC schemes for the network design to select: Centralized or Distributed. The Centralized scheme, which is not implementable in real networks can be used to determine the upper bound or best that can be achieved, and is to be used as a basis of comparison for real, implementable MAC algorithms. The Distributed MAC algorithm is based on the classic USAP (Unified Slot Assignment Protocol) [5] and is a good representation of “typical” TDMA MAC algorithms. Both algorithms include design selectable parameters of slots per frame and frame duration.

In Step-by-step mode, MAC tables are used to see how much of the required traffic load can be accommodated given the parameters chosen for the MAC and previous algorithms. The user can examine the tables at a high level by looking at the values as a whole or at a detailed level by looking at specific values. For example, at a high level, the user can see if there is a high amount of loss and/or delay accrued by the traffic flows. An example of looking at specific values is when the user wants to know which links received insufficient transmit time (slots in the USAP case) or which links were used the most.

4. CONCLUSION

NEDAT is a tool to assist network engineers get a sense of performance about the networks they design before the prototyping stage. It is still being development with improvements to user features, enhancements to current algorithms, and addition of algorithms to address other areas of the wireless networking design space. Such future enhancements and additional design areas include multicast, domain hierarchy, CSMA MAC, multiple interfaces on nodes, and scalability of algorithms.

Currently, NEDAT is used to compare performance of a specific set of network design parameters. In the next version, a more automated approach would be taken where multiple sets of parameters will be generated and

executed. The outputs of this will make the performance tradeoffs between design options more visible.

There are many areas in network design left unaddressed by this tool, but the challenge is to find appropriate research that has network design in mind. One area is the post-analysis problem: what network data is most important to the user, how to organize performance data for the user to understand, and what design decisions should the user make after viewing it. Another area is in solving resource shortfalls. NEDAT currently identifies shortfalls of what requirements are not met, but algorithms are needed to provide solutions to those shortfalls.

5. BIBLIOGRAPHY

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